

DIDACTIC MEANS OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7440693>

Tursunova Inobat Mirkamilovna

Teacher, National University of Uzbekistan

E- mail: i.tursunova@nuu.uz

Bazarova Shohida Ashirkulovna

Teacher, National University of Uzbekistan

E- mail: shohidabazarova25@gmail.com

ELSEVIER

Abstract: General didactics principles of teaching the Russian language is based on the teaching of science. Principles – are the first theoretical rules that determine the methods of the teacher’s activity. These rules can be applied in teaching all school subjects and therefore can be called general didactics, and can also contribute to and classify the organization of the qualitative assimilation of one of the subjects.

Keywords: methods, teaching, theory, trajectory, didactics, principle, scientific nature, subjects.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

Received: 13-12-2022

Accepted: 15-12-2022

Published: 22-12-2022

Teaching any subject is the basic principles of didactics and the initial theoretical rules that determine the trajectory of the teacher’s activity. These rules can be applied in teaching all school subjects and therefore can be called general didactics, and can also contribute to and classify the organization of the qualitative assimilation of one of the subjects. The teacher must be independent and proactive in choosing the most effective method and techniques, be able to analyze and evaluate the technique or method that he chooses for a particular task.

The main principles are:

- a) general didactics, which is applicable to all academic disciplines.
- b) specific didactics. This is unique to this theme, in our case - the Russian language.

The general didactic principles of teaching are: the principle of scientific, structured and consistent teaching; the rule of connection between theory and practice; the principle of interdependence of the various sections that make up the school course of the Russian language (spelling, punctuation, grammar with a dictionary, etc.); consciousness, principle of action; the rule of appearance, durability and convenience; principle of individual approach to students.

a) the relationship between language learning and the development of thinking;

(b) the relationship between the study of the grammatical structure of the language and the acquisition of literary reading skills;

c) the relationship between the study of grammar and the acquisition of speaking skills, etc.

The application of the scientific principle of teaching languages presupposes only the transfer to students of such knowledge - information about the language that has become firmly established in modern linguistics, the coverage of these phenomena in their interdependence and development.

For example, once in Russian textbooks the letters “и”, “о”, “е” were called soft vowels and from the point of view of modern science it was incorrect, and therefore now they are letters denoting sounds “а”, “ю”, “е” or the former softness (джа, джы, же).

From this point of view, for example, it seems more appropriate to study adjectives and numerals after the noun, rather than after the verb. They have more in common with a noun than with a verb. Or, for example, it is impossible to learn complex syntactic constructions before studying complex, compound sentences, invocations and introductory words - the first of the secondary members of the sentence.

In a broad sense, the connection between theory and practice lies in the relevance of learning for profession, in the ability to apply the knowledge gained at school in practical production and social activities.

In this regard, Russian language lessons can be considered organized only in the following cases, for example:

a) any grammatical position is illustrated with examples from authentic speech and fiction;

b) as a result of years of practice, students develop strong skills in the free application of theoretical knowledge in the construction of speech (oral and written), in the performance of various educational tasks and exercises (grammatical analysis, etc.).

Properly implemented subjects and interdisciplinary connections play an important role in teaching the Russian language. Mastering spelling is largely determined by students' knowledge of grammar, so spelling and punctuation are studied simultaneously with grammar, in their relationship. The study of morphology is inseparable from syntax, since many morphological phenomena (parts of speech, fixed suffixes, etc.) must also be considered as phenomena with certain syntactic properties. Classes for the development of speech are held in conjunction with classes in grammar, spelling and punctuation. Students learn the correct pronunciation in all Russian lessons, especially with knowledge of phonetics and teaching expressive reading. Almost all Russian language lessons, including spelling and grammar lessons, especially exercises with grammatical analysis, can be used to develop logical thinking, as well as work to enrich students' vocabulary.

All subjects in general and each in particular enrich the speech of individual students, strengthening spelling skills, especially the spelling of new words and

terms. Didactic principles, conversations, discussions serve as the basis for the development of oral speech for everyone in the study of not only the Russian language, but also geography, mathematics, physics, natural and other sciences.

REFERENCES:

1. Isakova Ravshana Karimzhanovna, & Begmatova Navruza Abdukhamedovna. (2021). THE NEXT STEP TO INNOVATION-ORIENTED EDUCATION IS THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES INTO THE PRACTICE OF TEACHING THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE GROUPS. *Archive of Conferences*, 33-34. Retrieved from <https://conferencepublication.com/index.php/aoc/article/view/1577>
2. Bazarova Sh. A, & Alimbaeva I. M. (2021). MODERN METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES OF ROLE PLAY IN TEACHING DIALOGUE. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(10), 218–221. Retrieved from <https://www.giirj.com/index.php/giirj/article/view/332>
3. Базарова Шохида Аширкуловна. Международная открытая конференция - Развитие творческой активности учащихся на уроках русского языка Vol. 1 No. 4 (2022): SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS AND TRENDS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH
4. Фарогат Юлдашева, Шахида Базарова.- Совершенствование методики преподавания грамматических понятий в неязыковых вузах – XXXVI Международной научно-практической интернет-конференции «Проблемы и перспективы развития современной науки в странах Европы и Азии» 2021 г.
5. Berdieva Mukarrama Anvarovna, Bazarova Shokhida Ashirkulovna- The role of authentic materials in teaching Russian language in higher education. Молодой ученый Международный научный журнал № 17 (412) / 2022
6. Бердиева Мукаррама Анваровна. Особенности работы над понятием «Стиль речи» Тульская международная конференция по преподаванию иностранных языков (tsul icon - flt).2021 г
7. Базарова Шохида Аширкуловна. Methodology of teaching the russian language in higher education. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali. 2022
8. Бердиева Мукаррама Анваровна. Modern methods of teaching russian as a foreign language in branches of foreign universities in Uzbekistan. Международный журнал исследований и разработок EPRA (IJRD) 2021.
9. Бердиева Мукаррама Анваровна. Вопросы формирования профессиональной компетентности в работе над стилями речи при обучении

русскому языку. Московский педагогический государственный университет
<http://nauka-i-shkola.ru/sites/default/files/171178.pdf>. 2019 г